

Participatory Approaches for Physical Activity Technologies in Older Adults: A Scoping Review Protocol

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Review Methods

In this section, you register the general type, background, and goals of your review.

Type of review *

This can be, for example, a meta-analysis, evidence map, or a qualitative review. Also indicate whether you used any guidelines, tools, or checklists to prepare your protocol and, if so, which ones. For more information, see: Tricco, A. C., Tetzlaff, J., Moher, D. (2011). The art and science of knowledge synthesis. <https://doi.org/frdpd2>.

Scoping Review

Review stages *

Indicate the stages in which you will conduct this review. Common stages are, in this order, the sections of this form: Search, Screening, Extraction, Synthesis. Sometimes other stages are distinguished, such as Preparation, Critical Appraisal, and Reporting. Additionally, it can be beneficial to include pilot stages for screening and extraction, while mentioning any updates to the preregistration. The stages could then look like: Preparation, Search, Pilot Screening (100 hits), Prereg Update, Screening, Pilot Extraction (10 sources), Prereg update, Extraction, Synthesis.

Preparation, Search, Screening, Extraction, Synthesis

Current review stage *

Indicate which stage from the “Review stages” item you are at this moment (i.e., when you freeze this registration). Note that in many contexts, only registrations in earlier stages are considered preregistrations. For example, you can indicate whether you started and/or finished with a certain stage as is customary for PROSPERO registrations. In addition, if this is not the first preregistration (but a second or third update, e.g., after pilot screening or pilot extraction), you can make that explicit here.

Search

Start date *

Indicate the planned start date, or if you already started, the actual start date.

01.09.2025

End date *

Indicate the planned end date, or if you already completed the review, the actual end date. You can use resources such as PredicTER.org to estimate how long a review will take to complete.

30.06.2026

Background *

Introduce the topic of your review, its aims, and/or provide a short summary of known literature and what your review adds to this literature. You can describe why the review is needed, as well as which reviews already exist on this or related topics.

Promoting physical activity in older adults is a public health priority, as regular activity contributes to maintaining functional independence, reducing chronic disease burden, and supporting mental and social well-being. Despite these well-established benefits, inactivity remains highly prevalent among older adults, and conventional interventions often fail to meet the complex, heterogeneous needs of this population. To enhance relevance and uptake, participatory approaches, including co-design, participatory design, and user-centered design, have increasingly been used to involve older adults directly in the development of health and physical activity interventions. These approaches aim to align technologies and programs with users' lived experiences, preferences, and functional capabilities, thereby improving feasibility, usability, and long-term adoption.

Several reviews illustrate the increasing relevance of participatory methods but also highlight substantial conceptual and methodological inconsistencies. A rapid review of digital participatory approaches in health intervention development identified a wide range of formats (e.g., online focus groups, digital mapping), noting both benefits such as flexibility and anonymity, and barriers including digital literacy demands and connectivity challenges (Doerwald et al., 2024). However, this review examined participatory digital methods across health domains, not specifically within physical activity promotion for older adults.

Research on co-designed physical activity interventions for older adults has also expanded. A recent scoping review mapped how co-design has been applied in physical activity intervention development, revealing substantial heterogeneity in terminology, levels of involvement, and operationalization of co-design. Most studies engaged older adults in a consultative or collaborative manner, while only one applied consumer control, and no studies assessed the effectiveness of the co-design process itself (Constantin et al., 2022). Complementary evidence from a systematic review and meta-analysis suggests that while co-designed interventions may be promising, current evidence is limited, of very low quality, and insufficient to determine whether co-design leads to measurably better physical activity outcomes than standard care (Zacharuk et al., 2024).

Beyond physical activity, participatory development of technology for aging in place shows similarly inconsistent reporting and variable outcomes. A systematic review found that while co-designed technologies may enhance usability and acceptability, evidence regarding health and well-being benefits remains limited, and barriers such as methodological variability, differing expectations, and the need for design expertise persist (Sumner et al., 2021).

Taken together, existing evidence demonstrates growing interest in participatory approaches for developing physical activity technologies for older adults, yet critical gaps remain. Current reviews either focus broadly on digital participatory methods across health topics, synthesize only co-designed physical activity interventions without focusing on technology, or examine technology co-design without linking to physical activity promotion. No review to date has systematically mapped how participatory approaches have been used specifically to develop technology-assisted physical activity interventions for older adults, nor how these approaches have been implemented, evaluated, or experienced.

This scoping review addresses this gap by mapping participatory methodologies, levels of involvement, resulting technologies, evaluation strategies, and reported barriers and facilitators in the development of technology-assisted physical activity interventions for older adults. It thereby provides a comprehensive overview to inform more rigorous, consistent, and meaningful participatory practices in future research and development.

Primary Objective:

To map the participatory approaches (terminology and definitions) used to develop technology-assisted physical activity interventions in older adults

Secondary Objectives:

- Describe the technologies that have been developed using participatory approaches aiming to promote physical activity interventions for older adults
- Determine the level of involvement of older adults (e.g. just consultative, vs collaboration, vs dissemination) in the applied participatory approaches to develop technology-assisted physical activity interventions in older adults
- Examine how the success (e.g. measuring participant satisfaction, adherence to the intervention etc.) and/or effectiveness of participatory approaches for physical activity technologies in older adults has been measured
- Identify barriers and facilitators for the participatory processes in technology-assisted physical activity interventions in older adults
- Synthesize the effects of participatory approaches for physical activity technologies in older adults on physical activity and/or other health-related outcomes

Primary research question(s) *

List the specific questions this review is meant to answer (i.e., the questions that ultimately informed the decisions made when designing the search strategy, and screening, extraction, and synthesis plans). You may find it helpful to refer to frameworks such as PICOS where appropriate to pinpoint your research questions. Note that all analyses pertaining to primary research questions should normally be reported in the final report.

What participatory approaches have been used to develop technology-assisted physical activity interventions for older adults?

What technologies have been developed using participatory approaches to promote physical activity in older adults?

Secondary research question(s) *

List additional research questions that you will examine, but that took less central roles in informing the review's design. Note that all analyses pertaining to secondary research questions should normally be reported in the final report.

What is the level of involvement of older adults in participatory approaches for technology-assisted physical activity interventions?

How is the success and/or efficacy of the participatory approaches for technology-assisted physical activity interventions measured?

What are barriers and facilitators for the applied participatory approaches?

What are the effects of participatory approaches for technology-assisted physical activity promotion in older adults?

Expectations / hypotheses *

Describe any hypotheses (common for quantitative approaches) and/or expectations you have. These can pertain to your research questions, the types of sources you will find, social and political contexts, and contextual information that you know may color your interpretations and decisions (common for qualitative approaches).

Since we are conducting a scoping review, our approach is exploratory rather than confirmatory. Thus, we do not test hypotheses but rather map, describe, and categorize existing evidence to clarify what is known and where gaps exist.

We expect the following:

Participatory design approaches (e.g., co-design, user-centered design, living labs) are increasingly used in developing technology-assisted physical activity interventions for older adults.

The extent and depth of older adults' involvement in these participatory processes vary considerably, often remaining limited to consultation or prototype testing stages.

Most technologies developed using participatory methods focus on motivation, adherence, and feedback rather than on complex components.

There is likely a mismatch between the participatory principles reported (e.g., co-creation) and their practical implementation in published studies.

Dependent variable(s) / outcome(s) / main variables *

List the dependent / outcome / main variables you are interested in. If this review concerns one or more associations, list the outcome variable(s) or dependent variables. If this review does not concern one or more associations (e.g., in reviews of single variables such as prevalences, or descriptive reviews), list the main variables of interest here.

This scoping review does not test relationships between variables. However, conceptually, the independent variables/outcomes are the characteristics of participatory approaches and technologies used to promote physical activity in older adults.

- Type of participatory approach used (e.g., co-design, co-creation, user-centered design, participatory action research, living lab).
- Level and/or nature of involvement of older adults in the design process (e.g., consultative, collaborative, co-leading).
- Type of technology developed (e.g., exergames, wearable activity monitors, mobile applications, tele-rehabilitation systems).
- Target behavior or intervention aim (e.g., promoting physical activity, reducing sedentary behavior, improving functional capacity or mobility).
- Context of implementation (e.g., community-based, clinical, home environment).
- Stakeholders involved (e.g., researchers, designers, clinicians, caregivers).

Independent variable(s) / intervention(s) / treatment(s) *

If this review's research question(s) concerns one or more associations or effects, list the variable(s) that theoretically cause them or are assumed to otherwise explain the dependent variable(s) / outcome(s). If this is a manipulation, treatment, or intervention, make sure to describe it in full: that means also describing all groups, including any control group(s) or comparator(s).

This scoping review does not test relationships between variables. However, conceptually, dependent variables are the reported outcomes, including the success, barriers, facilitators, and effects of these participatory approaches on intervention design and physical activity outcomes.

- Success or efficacy measures of the participatory approach (e.g., user satisfaction, usability, adoption, adherence, engagement).
- Effects on physical activity outcomes (e.g., changes in PA levels, mobility, or health-related indicators in older adults).
- Perceived barriers and facilitators to implementation or collaboration.
- Reported impact on intervention quality, feasibility, or acceptance.
- Extent to which participatory processes influence technology design, uptake, and sustainability.

Additional variable(s) / covariate(s) *

Here, list any additional variables you are interested in that were not included in the two lists above, such as covariates, moderators, or mediators.

In this scoping review, additional contextual variables will be extracted and may act as potential moderators or descriptors influencing the implementation and outcomes of participatory approaches. These include:

- Participant characteristics:
 - age, sex, health status, functional or cognitive level
- Stakeholder composition:
 - type and number of stakeholders engaged (e.g., designers, clinicians, caregivers, policymakers).
- Geographical and cultural context:
 - country or region, sociocultural setting, and technological infrastructure.
- Study design and methodology:
 - qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-method design; phase of participation (design, development, evaluation).
- Duration and intensity of participation:
 - frequency and length of participatory sessions, stages of involvement across the project lifecycle.
- Technology maturity:
 - prototype vs. finalized product; technology readiness level (TRL).
- Setting of intervention or development:
 - community, clinical, rehabilitation, or home-based environments.
- Funding or institutional context:
 - academic, industrial, or public-sector collaborations.

These variables will not be analyzed as statistical covariates but will serve to contextualize and map the variability across studies regarding how participatory approaches are implemented and reported.

Software *

List the software you will use for the review, for instance to store and screen search results, extract data, keep track of decisions, and to synthesize the results. Include version numbers and operating systems, if applicable.

All references from all databases will be imported in EndNote where duplicates will be removed.

Rayyan will be used to for title/abstract and full-text screening

RedCap will be used for Data Extraction

Funding *

List the funding sources for everybody that is involved in this review at this stage. If the work is unfunded, please state this as such.

This work is conducted without additional/external funding

Conflicts of interest *

List any potential conflicts of interest (e.g., if there is a potential outcome of this review that can in any way have negative or positive effects for anybody involved in this review in terms of funding, prestige, or opportunities). If there are no conflicts of interest, please state this as such.

The authors report no conflict of interest

Overlapping authorships *

Declare whether you expect that anyone involved in this review is a co-author of one of the studies that will likely be included in the review (based on your search strategy) and, if so, how you will address potential bias (i.e., that reviewer is not involved in screening, data extraction,

quality assessment, or synthesis of that study). If you are confident that this does not represent a conflict of interest, explain why you think so.

n.a.

Search Strategy

In this section, you register your search strategy: the procedures you designed to obtain all (potentially) relevant sources to review (e.g., articles, books, preprints, reports, case law, policy papers, archived documents).

Databases *

List the databases you will search (e.g., ArXiv, PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, PsycINFO, AGRIS, BioOne, PubChem). Note that these are different from interfaces (see next question).

1. MEDLINE
2. SCOPUS
3. CINAHL
4. PSYCINFO
5. EMBASE
6. PROQUEST

Interfaces *

For each database, list the interface you used to search that database (e.g., Ovid or EBSCO). Some databases are provided by the same organisation, in which case the interface can have the same name (e.g., PubMed, ArXiv). For more information about the distinction.

MEDLINE, EMBASE and PSYCINFO via Ovid
CINAHL via EBSCO
SCOPUS via Elsevier
PROQUEST via PROQUEST

Grey literature *

List your strategies for locating grey literature (i.e., sources not indexed in the databases you search) such as pre-prints (e.g., disciplinary repositories such as ArXiv or PsyArXiv or university repositories using for example, DSpace), dissertations and theses, conference proceedings and abstracts, government/industry reports etc.

Grey literature was searched using ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global to identify relevant theses. A simplified keyword-based search strategy was applied using terms related to participatory approaches, older adults, technology, and physical activity.

("participatory" OR "co-design")
AND ("older adults" OR older people OR ageing OR aging)
AND (technology OR eHealth OR mHealth OR digital)
AND ("physical activity" OR exercise)

Inclusion and exclusion criteria *

List the specific inclusion and exclusion criteria that you used to inform your search strategy. Also list the framework(s) you used to establish your exclusion and inclusion criteria and use them to develop your search query, if any. Examples of the latter are PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome) and SPIDER (Sample, Phenomenon of Interest, Design, Evaluation, Research type), but many more exist.

	Include	Exclude
Population	Adults older than 60 years	Studies with participants residing in nursing homes, hospices, or those receiving inpatient hospital care are ineligible

Intervention	Physical Activity-related technology co-designed with the target population including information communication technologies, mobile and electronic health solutions.	
Control	All types of control groups	No exclusion criteria in terms of types of control groups
Outcomes		
Study Design	Any type of study that reports on PA-related technology development	
Language	English	
Timeframe	2010 onwards	

Query strings *

For each database/interface combination, list the query you will input (note that the available fields and operators can differ by database and by interface). The query string can be based on, for example, your inclusion criteria, the entities you want to extract (see “extraction”) and design requirements (e.g., qualitative studies, RCTs, or prevalence studies).

MEDLINE via Ovid 250703

Query
(Aged or Aging or Ageing or "Older adults" or "Older people" or Elder* or Senior or Old or geriatric).ti,ab,kw,kf.
exp Aged/
("Participatory approach*" or "Participatory intervention*" or Co-management or Co-production or Co-creation or "Action research" or "Participatory design" or Co-design or "User centered design" or "User centred design" or "participatory research" or Co-Learning or "Stakeholder involvement" or "User Involvement" or "User Participation" or "Patient Participation" or "Community Participation").ti,ab,kw,kf.

exp Community-Based Participatory Research/ or exp Patient Participation/ or exp Community Participation/

(exercis* or "Physical activit*" or Recreation or "Motor Activi*" or Movement* or Sports or "Activit* of Daily Living" or Fitness or Walk* or "Physical Endurance" or gymnastics or Run* or Swim* or Treadmill or "Physical effort" or workout or "Dance therapy").ti,ab,kw,kf.

((Aerobic* or Aerobic*) adj3 (danc* or step)).ti,ab,kw,kf.

((Physical or Functional) adj3 Performance*).ti,ab,kw,kf.

(Activit* adj2 ("daily living" or "daily li*" or Mobility)).ti,ab,kw,kf.

exp Exercise/ or exp Sports/ or exp Physical Fitness/ or exp Exercise Therapy/ or exp Recreation/ or exp Recreation Therapy/ or exp Motor Activity/ or exp Sports Equipment/ or exp "Activities of Daily Living"/ or exp Exercise Movement Techniques/ or exp Physical Endurance/ or Physical Functional Performance/ or Dance Therapy/

(E-health or ehealth or Technology or "Technical systems" or Telemedicine or Telerehabilitation or "Medical Informatics Applications" or "Computer-assisted" or "Electronic mail" or E-mail or Video* or Computer* or Internet or Cellphone* or "Cellular Radio*" or "Mobile radiotelephone*" or "Wireless handset*" or Smartphone* or Text* or "Text Messag*" or "Short Messag* Service*" or "Multimedia messag* service*" or "Picture messag*" or "Video messag*" or "Digital health*" or Facebook or Flickr or hashtag or Instagram or LinkedIn or MySpace or Pinterest or Reddit or "Sina Weibo" or Snapchat or TikTok or Tumblr or Twitter or WeChat or WhatsApp or YouTube or "Electronic Messag*" or "Electronic correspondence*" or "Electronic Mail*" or "Remote consultation" or m-health or Mhealth or "Wireless communication" or telecare or "Mobile health" or "internet connection" or Website or Web or "Information retrieval system" or "World Wide Web" or Teleconsultation* or "tele-consultation*" or " telephone consultation*" or "telephone-based consultation*" or "telephone based consultation*" or e-counseling or Telecommunication* or Videoconferenc* or Esport or E-sport or "Artificial intelligence" or VR or "Virtual reality" or Gamification or Exergam*).ti,ab,kw,kf.

(("on line" or "on-line" or online) adj2 system*).ti,ab,kw,kf.

(digital adj3 (system* or electronic* or technolog*)).ti,ab,kw,kf.

((Mobile or Cell* or Wireless or Smart) adj3 (Phone* or Telephone* or headset*)).ti,ab,kw,kf.

((Tablet* or Slate* or Portable or Pad* or Hand-held) adj3 (Comput* or Touch-screen* or Touchscreen*)).ti,ab,kw,kf.

(Touch adj3 (panel* or Screen*)).ti,ab,kw,kf.

((Mobile or "Portable Software" or Smartphone* or "Portable Electronic*" or tablet) adj3 App*).ti,ab,kw,kf.

(("internet of thing*" or "Internet or web" or Online) adj3 (us* or Util* or Access)).ti,ab,kw,kf.

(social adj2 (networking or platform* or media)).ti,ab,kw,kf.

exp Medical Informatics Applications/ or exp Decision Making, Computer-Assisted/ or exp Diagnosis, Computer-Assisted/ or exp Therapy, Computer-Assisted/ or exp Electronic Mail/ or exp Videoconferencing/ or Computers/ or exp Computers, Handheld/ or exp Internet/ or exp Internet of Things/ or exp Internet Access/ or exp Social Media/ or exp Telephone/ or exp Cell Phone/ or exp Remote Consultation/ or exp Distance Counseling/ or exp Online Systems/ or exp Digital Technology/ or exp Smartphone/ or exp Text Messaging/ or exp Telerehabilitation/ or exp Telemedicine/ or exp Artificial Intelligence/ or exp Virtual Reality/ or exp Gamification/ or exp Exergaming/

1 or 2

3 or 4

5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9

or/10-19

20 and 21 and 22 and 23

(Child* or Youth or adolescen*).ti,ab,kw,kf.

exp Child/ or exp Adolescent/

25 or 26

24 not 27

CINAHL via Ebsco 250703

Query
S27 NOT S26 Limiters - Peer Reviewed; Exclude MEDLINE records
S27 NOT S26
S22 AND S23 AND S24 AND S25
S20 OR S21
S10 OR S11 OR S12 OR S13 OR S14 OR S15 OR S16 OR S17 OR S18 OR S19
S5 OR S6 OR S7 OR S8 OR S9
S3 OR S4
S1 OR S2
(MH "Child+") OR (MH "Adolescence+")
TI (child or youth or adolescen*) OR AB (child or youth or adolescen*)

(MH "Medical Informatics") OR (MH "Mobile Applications") OR (MH "Health Informatics+") OR (MH "Decision Making, Computer Assisted+") OR (MH "Diagnosis, Computer Assisted+") OR (MH "Computer-Assisted Instruction") OR (MH "Email") OR (MH "Videoconferencing+") OR (MH "Telemedicine+") OR (MH "Telehealth+") OR (MH "Computers and Computerization+") OR (MH "Computers, Portable+") OR (MH "Computers, Hand-Held+") OR (MH "Internet+") OR (MH "Internet Access") OR (MH "Internet of Things") OR (MH "Internet Searching") OR (MH "World Wide Web+") OR (MH "World Wide Web Applications+") OR (MH "Social Media+") OR (MH "Telephone+") OR (MH "Cellular Phone+") OR (MH "Smartphone") OR (MH "Wireless Communications") OR (MH "Remote Consultation") OR (MH "Online Systems+") OR (MH "Digital Technology+") OR (MH "Text Messaging+") OR (MH "Telerehabilitation") OR (MH "Artificial Intelligence+") OR (MH "Virtual Reality+") OR (MH "Gamification") OR (MH "Exergames")

TI (social N2 (networking or platform* or media)) OR AB (social N2 (networking or platform* or media))

TI (("internet of thing*" or "Internet or web" or Online) N3 (us* or Util* or Access)) OR AB (("internet of thing*" or "Internet or web" or Online) N3 (us* or Util* or Access))

TI ((Mobile or "Portable Software" or Smartphone* or "Portable Electronic*" or tablet) N3 App*) OR AB ((Mobile or "Portable Software" or Smartphone* or "Portable Electronic*" or tablet) N3 App*)

TI (Touch N3 (panel* or Screen*)) OR AB (Touch N3 (panel* or Screen*))

TI ((Tablet* or Slate* or Portable or Pad* or Hand-held) N3 (Comput* or Touch-screen* or Touchscreen*)) OR AB ((Tablet* or Slate* or Portable or Pad* or Hand-held) N3 (Comput* or Touch-screen* or Touchscreen*))

TI ((Mobile or Cell* or Wireless or Smart) N3 (Phone* or Telephone* or headset*)) OR AB ((Mobile or Cell* or Wireless or Smart) N3 (Phone* or Telephone* or headset*))

TI (digital N3 (system* or electronic* or technolog*)) OR AB (digital N3 (system* or electronic* or technolog*))

TI (("on line" or "on-line" or online) N2 system*) OR AB (("on line" or "on-line" or online) N2 system*)

TI (E-health or ehealth or Technology or "Technical systems" or Telemedicine or Telerehabilitation or "Medical Informatics Applications" or "Computer-assisted" or "Electronic mail" or E-mail or Video* or Computer* or Internet or Cellphone* or "Cellular Radio*" or "Mobile radiotelephone*" or "Wireless handset*" or Smartphone* or Text* or "Text Messag*" or "Short Messag* Service*" or "Multimedia messag* service*" or "Picture messag*" or "Video messag*" or "Digital health*" or Facebook or Flickr or hashtag or Instagram or LinkedIn or MySpace or Pinterest or Reddit or "Sina Weibo" or Snapchat or TikTok or Tumblr or Twitter or WeChat or WhatsApp or YouTube or "Electronic Messag*" or "Electronic correspondence*" or "Electronic Mail*" or "Remote consultation" or m-health or Mhealth or "Wireless communication" or telecare or "Mobile health" or "internet connection" or Website or Web or "Information retrieval system" or "World Wide Web" or Teleconsultation* or "tele-consultation*" or " telephone consultation*" or "telephone-based consultation*" or "telephone based consultation*" or e-counseling or Telecommunication* or Videoconferenc* or Esport or E-sport or "Artificial intelligence" or VR or "Virtual reality" or Gamification or Exergam*) OR AB (E-health or ehealth or Technology or "Technical systems" or Telemedicine or Telerehabilitation or "Medical Informatics Applications" or "Computer-assisted" or "Electronic mail" or E-mail or Video* or Computer* or Internet or Cellphone* or "Cellular Radio*" or "Mobile radiotelephone*" or "Wireless handset*" or Smartphone* or Text* or "Text Messag*" or "Short Messag* Service*" or "Multimedia messag* service*" or "Picture messag*" or "Video messag*" or "Digital health*" or Facebook or Flickr or hashtag or Instagram or LinkedIn or MySpace or Pinterest or Reddit or "Sina Weibo" or Snapchat or TikTok or Tumblr or Twitter or WeChat or WhatsApp or YouTube or "Electronic Messag*" or "Electronic correspondence*" or "Electronic Mail*" or "Remote consultation" or m-health or Mhealth or "Wireless communication" or telecare or "Mobile health" or "internet connection" or Website or Web or "Information retrieval system" or "World Wide Web" or Teleconsultation* or "tele-consultation*" or " telephone consultation*" or "telephone-based consultation*" or "telephone based consultation*" or e-counseling or Telecommunication* or Videoconferenc* or Esport or E-sport or "Artificial intelligence" or VR or "Virtual reality" or Gamification or Exergam*)

(MH "Exercise+") OR (MH "Therapeutic Exercise+") OR (MH "Physical Activity") OR (MH "Sports+") OR (MH "Physical Fitness+") OR (MH "Recreation+") OR (MH "Recreational Therapy") OR (MH "Motor Activity+") OR (MH "Sports Equipment and Supplies+") OR (MH "Activities of Daily Living+") OR (MH "Physical Endurance+") OR (MH "Physical Performance") OR (MH "Dance Therapy") OR (MH "Aerobic Dancing")

Activit* N2 ("daily living" or "daily li*" or Mobility)

TI ((Physical or Functional) N3 Performance*) OR AB ((Physical or Functional) N3 Performance*)

TI ((Aerobic* or Aerobic*) N3 (danc* or step)) OR AB ((Aerobic* or Aerobic*) N3 (danc* or step))

TI (exercis* or "Physical activit*" or Recreation or "Motor Activi*" or Movement* or Sports or "Activit* of Daily Living" or Fitness or Walk* or "Physical Endurance" or gymnastics or Run* or Swim* or Treadmill or "Physical effort" or workout or "Dance therapy") OR AB (exercis* or "Physical activit*" or Recreation or "Motor Activi*" or Movement* or Sports or "Activit* of Daily Living" or Fitness or Walk* or "Physical Endurance" or gymnastics or Run* or Swim* or Treadmill or "Physical effort" or workout or "Dance therapy")

(MH "Patient Participation+") OR (MH "Stakeholder Participation") OR (MH "Consumer Participation+") OR (MH "Sports Participation")

TI ("Participatory approach*" or "Participatory intervention*" or Co-management or Co-production or Co-creation or "Action research" or "Participatory design" or Co-design or "User centered design" or "User centred design" or "participatory research" or Co-Learning or "Stakeholder involvement" or "User Involvement" or "User Participation" or "Patient Participation" or "Community Participation") OR AB ("Participatory approach*" or "Participatory intervention*" or Co-management or Co-production or Co-creation or "Action research" or "Participatory design" or Co-design or "User centered design" or "User centred design" or "participatory research" or Co-Learning or "Stakeholder involvement" or "User Involvement" or "User Participation" or "Patient Participation" or "Community Participation")

(MH "Aged+")

TI (Aged or Aging or Ageing or "Older adults" or "Older people" or Elder* or Senior or Old or geriatric) OR AB (Aged or Aging or Ageing or "Older adults" or "Older people" or Elder* or Senior or Old or geriatric)

Proquest 250703

Search terms used:

"Participatory approach" "older adults" E-health "physical activity"

PsycInfo 250906

Query
(Aged or Aging or Ageing or "Older adults" or "Older people" or Elder* or Senior or Old or geriatric).ti,ab,id.
("Participatory approach*" or "Participatory intervention*" or Co-management or Co-production or Co-creation or "Action research" or "Participatory design" or Co-design or "User centered design" or "User centred design" or "participatory research" or Co-Learning or "Stakeholder involvement" or "User Involvement" or "User Participation" or "Patient Participation" or "Community Participation").ti,ab,id.
exp Community-Based Participatory Research/ or exp Client Participation/ or exp Community Involvement/
(exercis* or "Physical activit*" or Recreation or "Motor Activi*" or Movement* or Sports or "Activit* of Daily Living" or Fitness or Walk* or "Physical Endurance" or gymnastics or Run* or Swim* or Treadmill or "Physical effort" or workout or "Dance therapy").ti,ab,id.
((Aerobic* or Aerobic*) adj3 (danc* or step)).ti,ab,id.
((Physical or Functional) adj3 Performance*).ti,ab,id.
(Activit* adj2 ("daily living" or "daily li*" or Mobility)).ti,ab,id.
exp Exercise/ or exp Sports/ or exp Physical Fitness/ or exp Exercise Therapy/ or exp Recreation/ or Recreation Therapy/ or exp "Activities of Daily Living"/ or exp Physical Endurance/ or exp Physical Activity/ or exp Dance Therapy/ or exp Aerobic Exercise/

(E-health or ehealth or Technology or "Technical systems" or Telemedicine or Telerehabilitation or "Medical Informatics Applications" or "Computer-assisted" or "Electronic mail" or E-mail or Video* or Computer* or Internet or Cellphone* or "Cellular Radio*" or "Mobile radiotelephone*" or "Wireless handset*" or Smartphone* or Text* or "Text Messag*" or "Short Messag* Service*" or "Multimedia messag* service*" or "Picture messag*" or "Video messag*" or "Digital health*" or Facebook or Flickr or hashtag or Instagram or LinkedIn or MySpace or Pinterest or Reddit or "Sina Weibo" or Snapchat or TikTok or Tumblr or Twitter or WeChat or WhatsApp or YouTube or "Electronic Messag*" or "Electronic correspondence*" or "Electronic Mail*" or "Remote consultation" or m-health or Mhealth or "Wireless communication" or telecare or "Mobile health" or "internet connection" or Website or Web or "Information retrieval system" or "World Wide Web" or Teleconsultation* or "tele-consultation*" or " telephone consultation*" or "telephone-based consultation*" or "telephone based consultation*" or e-counseling or Telecommunication* or Videoconferenc* or Esport or E-sport or "Artificial intelligence" or VR or "Virtual reality" or Gamification or Exergam*).ti,ab,id.

((("on line" or "on-line" or online) adj2 system*).ti,ab,id.

(digital adj3 (system* or electronic* or technolog*).ti,ab,id.

((Mobile or Cell* or Wireless or Smart) adj3 (Phone* or Telephone* or headset*).ti,ab,id.

((Tablet* or Slate* or Portable or Pad* or Hand-held) adj3 (Comput* or Touch-screen* or Touchscreen*).ti,ab,id.

(Touch adj3 (panel* or Screen*).ti,ab,id.

((Mobile or "Portable Software" or Smartphone* or "Portable Electronic*" or tablet) adj3 App*).ti,ab,id.

((("internet of thing*" or "Internet or web" or Online) adj3 (us* or Util* or Access)).ti,ab,id.

(social adj2 (networking or platform* or media)).ti,ab,id.

exp Digital Technology/ or exp Computer Assisted Instruction/ or exp Computer Assisted Diagnosis/ or exp Computer Assisted Therapy/ or exp Computer Mediated Communication/ or exp Videoconferencing/ or exp Computers/ or exp Internet/ or exp Internet Access/ or exp Social Media/ or exp Mobile Phones/ or exp Smartphones/ or exp Text Messaging/ or exp Telerehabilitation/ or exp Telemedicine/ or exp Artificial Intelligence/ or exp Virtual Reality/ or exp Gamification/

2 or 3

4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8

9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16 or 17 or 18

19 and 20 and 21

(Child* or Youth or adolescen*).ti,ab,id.

22 not 23

Embase 250906

Query

(Aged or Aging or Ageing or "Older adults" or "Older people" or Elder* or Senior or Old or geriatric).ti,ab,kf,kw.

exp aged/

("Participatory approach*" or "Participatory intervention*" or Co-management or Co-production or Co-creation or "Action research" or "Participatory design" or Co-design or "User centered design" or "User centred design" or "participatory research" or Co-Learning or "Stakeholder involvement" or "User Involvement" or "User Participation" or "Patient Participation" or "Community Participation").ti,ab,kw,kf.

exp participatory research/ or exp patient participation/ or exp community participation/

(exercis* or "Physical activit*" or Recreation or "Motor Activi*" or Movement* or Sports or "Activit* of Daily Living" or Fitness or Walk* or "Physical Endurance" or gymnastics or Run* or Swim* or Treadmill or "Physical effort" or workout or "Dance therapy").ti,ab,kw,kf.

((Aerobic* or Aerobic*) adj3 (danc* or step)).ti,ab,kw,kf.

((Physical or Functional) adj3 Performance*).ti,ab,kw,kf.

(Activit* adj2 ("daily living" or "daily li*" or Mobility)).ti,ab,kw,kf.

exp aerobic exercise/ or exp exercise/ or exp sport/ or exp fitness/ or exp physical activity/ or exp kinesiotherapy/ or exp recreation/ or exp recreational therapy/ or exp motor activity/ or exp sports equipment/ or exp daily life activity/ or exp endurance/ or exp physical performance/ or exp dance therapy/

(E-health or ehealth or Technology or "Technical systems" or Telemedicine or Telerehabilitation or "Medical Informatics Applications" or "Computer-assisted" or "Electronic mail" or E-mail or Video* or Computer* or Internet or Cellphone* or "Cellular Radio*" or "Mobile radiotelephone*" or "Wireless handset*" or Smartphone* or Text* or "Text Messag*" or "Short Messag* Service*" or "Multimedia messag* service*" or "Picture messag*" or "Video messag*" or "Digital health*" or Facebook or Flickr or hashtag or Instagram or LinkedIn or MySpace or Pinterest or Reddit or "Sina Weibo" or Snapchat or TikTok or Tumblr or Twitter or WeChat or WhatsApp or YouTube or "Electronic Messag*" or "Electronic correspondence*" or "Electronic Mail*" or "Remote consultation" or m-health or Mhealth or "Wireless communication" or telecare or "Mobile health" or "internet connection" or Website or Web or "Information retrieval system" or "World Wide Web" or Teleconsultation* or "tele-consultation*" or " telephone consultation*" or "telephone-based consultation*" or "telephone based consultation*" or e-counseling or Telecommunication*

or Videoconferenc* or Esport or E-sport or "Artificial intelligence" or VR or "Virtual reality" or Gamification or Exergam*).ti,ab,kw,kf.

((("on line" or "on-line" or online) adj2 system*).ti,ab,kw,kf.

(digital adj3 (system* or electronic* or technolog*).ti,ab,kw,kf.

((Mobile or Cell* or Wireless or Smart) adj3 (Phone* or Telephone* or headset*).ti,ab,kw,kf.

((Tablet* or Slate* or Portable or Pad* or Hand-held) adj3 (Comput* or Touch-screen* or Touchscreen*).ti,ab,kw,kf.

(Touch adj3 (panel* or Screen*).ti,ab,kw,kf.

((Mobile or "Portable Software" or Smartphone* or "Portable Electronic*" or tablet) adj3 App*).ti,ab,kw,kf.

((("internet of thing*" or "Internet or web" or Online) adj3 (us* or Util* or Access)).ti,ab,kw,kf.

(social adj2 (networking or platform* or media)).ti,ab,kw,kf.

exp medical informatics/ or exp decision support system/ or exp computer assisted diagnosis/ or exp computer assisted therapy/ or exp e-mail/ or exp videoconferencing/ or exp computer/ or exp personal digital assistant/ or exp Internet/ or exp "internet of things"/ or exp internet access/ or exp social media/ or exp telephone/ or exp mobile phone/ or exp teleconsultation/ or exp e-counseling/ or exp online system/ or exp digital technology/ or exp smartphone/ or exp text messaging/ or exp telerehabilitation/ or exp telemedicine/ or exp artificial intelligence/ or exp virtual reality/ or exp gamification/ or exp exergaming/ or exp telecommunication/

1 or 2

3 or 4

5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9

10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16 or 17 or 18 or 19

20 and 21 and 22 and 23

exp child/ or exp adolescent/

(Child* or Youth or adolescen*).ti,ab,kw,kf.

25 or 26

24 not 27

Scopus

TITLE-ABS(Aged or Aging or Ageing or {Older adults} or {Older people} or Elder* or Senior or Old or geriatric) AND TITLE-ABS({Participatory approach*} or {Participatory intervention*} or Co-management or Co-production or Co-creation or {Action research} or {Participatory design} or Co-design or {User centered design} or {User centred design} or {participatory research} or

Co-Learning or {Stakeholder involvement} or {User Involvement} or {User Participation} or {Patient Participation} or {Community Participation}) AND TITLE-ABS(exercis* or {Physical activit*} or Recreation or {Motor Activi*} or Movement* or Sports or {Activit* of Daily Living} or Fitness or Walk* or {Physical Endurance} or gymnastics or Run* or Swim* or Treadmill or {Physical effort} or workout or {Dance therapy}) AND TITLE-ABS(E-health or ehealth or Technology or {Technical systems} or Telemedicine or Telerehabilitation or {Medical Informatics Applications} or {Computer-assisted} or {Electronic mail} or E-mail or Video* or Computer* or Internet or Cellphone* or {Cellular Radio*} or {Mobile radiotelephone*} or {Wireless handset*} or Smartphone* or Text* or {Text Messag*} or {Short Messag* Service*} or {Multimedia messag* service*} or {Picture messag*} or {Video messag*} or {Digital health*} or Facebook or Flickr or hashtag or Instagram or LinkedIn or MySpace or Pinterest or Reddit or {Sina Weibo} or Snapchat or TikTok or Tumblr or Twitter or WeChat or WhatsApp or YouTube or {Electronic Messag*} or {Electronic correspondence*} or {Electronic Mail*} or {Remote consultation} or m-health or Mhealth or {Wireless communication} or telecare or {Mobile health} or {internet connection} or Website or Web or {Information retrieval system} or {World Wide Web} or Teleconsultation* or {tele-consultation*} or {telephone consultation*} or {telephone-based consultation*} or {telephone based consultation*} or e-counseling or Telecommunication* or Videoconferenc* or Esport or E-sport or {Artificial intelligence} or VR or {Virtual reality} or Gamification or Exergam*) AND NOT TITLE-ABS(Child* or adolescent* or youth

Search validation procedure *

Explain whether you plan to employ a search validation procedure, and if so, describe the procedure. For example, you can use a number of sources that you know your search strategy will have to turn up to validate your strategy and make adjustments if needed.

n.a

Other search strategies *

List any additional search strategies you aim to employ, such as using the ascendancy approach (look through other sources cited in your included sources), the descendancy approach (look through the sources that cite your included sources using systems such as Crossref), or using other systems such as CoCites.

No other search strategies will be applied.

Procedures to contact authors *

Describe your procedures for contacting authors. Will you contact authors? When? How will you follow-up on your first contact? Do you plan to share meta-data about those communications, and if so, how do you ask authors' permission for that? Note that templates are available at <https://osf.io/q8stz/>

We do not plan to contact authors for further data requests.

Results of contacting authors *

Describe whether you plan to report the outcomes of contacting the authors (e.g., how many authors responded, how many authors sent data), and if so, how.

n.a

Search expiration and repetition *

Depending on how quickly the literature in an area expands, searches can have limited expiration dates; and for living reviews, repetition is planned regardless of ideas about expiration. Will you repeat your search (for example, in the case of a living review), and if so, how many months or years after your first search?

We do not plan to repeat the search.

Search strategy justification *

Search strategies are often compromises, balancing pragmatic considerations with scientific rigour. Here, describe the justifications for your decisions about the databases, interfaces, grey literature strategies, query strings, author contact procedures, and search expiration date.

The databases we chose are all within medicine and health, with the exception of ProQuest and Scopus, which are also multidisciplinary. The databases have indexed many journals, and to ensure that the search is comprehensive, we therefore chose to search in multiple databases.

The search strategy was based on the PCC framework, and keywords were selected along the way using test searches on various platforms. Additionally, we were also mindful of using the databases' own thesauri.

Miscellaneous search strategy details *

Here, you can describe any details that are not captured in the other fields in this section.

n.a

Screening

In this section, you register your screening procedure: the procedure you designed to eliminate all irrelevant sources from the results of the search strategy (and retain the relevant sources).

Screening stages *

Describe the stages you will use for screening. For example, if you expect many hits, you may want to first screen based on titles only, in a second round also include abstracts and keywords, and in a third round screen based on full texts. Also indicate for each round whether the screening is done by a computer (e.g., AI), a human, or a computer supervised by a human. Don't forget to describe the deduplication procedure, if you implement it.

Screening will be conducted in 2 phases:

1. Title and Abstract
2. Full-text

Screened fields / blinding *

Describe which bibliographic fields (e.g., title, abstract, authors) are visible during the screening, and which fields are blinded. For example, journal names, authors, and publication years can be hidden from screeners in an effort to minimize bias.

No bibliographic fields will be hidden from screeners

Used exclusion criteria *

List the specific exclusion criteria that you apply in your screening to eliminate sources from the set of sources identified in your search. Note that inclusion criteria are typically used to inform the search strategy; during screening, as soon as an exclusion criterion is met, an entry is excluded, and so, inclusion criteria are reformulated into exclusion criteria where applicable.

Sources were excluded if they focused on children (or adolescents) rather than older adults

Screener instructions *

List the instructions provided to the screener(s). You can also specify which file in the associated OSF project contains these instructions.

Screening reliability *

For each screening round, list the number of screeners and the procedure used to ensure independent screening. This can also mean that you declare that you only use one screener, use multiple screeners that work together, or that you will not implement procedures to ensure that the screening is conducted independently. Also explain the test you will use, if any, to assess screener agreement.

All references will be screened by 2 independent reviewers. Blinding will be applied using the available function in Rayyan.

Screening reconciliation procedure *

If you use more than one screener, describe the procedure to deal with divergent screener decisions for each screener round (e.g., through discussion or input from an additional screener).

Conflicts will be solved by a third screener.

Sampling and sample size *

Describe whether you plan to use all sources included through the screening procedure, or whether you plan to sample from these sources (note that in most cases, all studies identified at this stage are kept). In case of the latter, describe the procedure you plan to use, the sample size analyses you conducted or will conduct, and the resulting required sample size if that is already available. If you plan to refrain from drawing conclusions, or draw more nuanced conclusions, describe that here as well. Finally, describe what you will do if a minimum required sample size or power is not reached (for your main analysis and any supplementary analyses).

n.a

Screening procedure justification *

Screening procedures are often compromises, balancing pragmatic considerations with scientific rigour. Here, describe the justifications for your decisions about the screening rounds, blinding, in/exclusion criteria, assurance, and reconciliation procedures.

n.a

Data management and sharing *

Describe whether and how you plan to share the sources you obtained from the searches in the databases (see Search Strategy) and the decisions each screener made in each screening round. List both the file format (e.g., BibTeX, RIS, CSV, XLSX), the repository, and any potential embargos or conditions for access.

n.a

Miscellaneous screening details *

Here, you can describe any details that are not captured in the other fields in this section.

n.a

Extraction

In this section, you register your plans for data extraction: the procedures you designed to extract the data you are interested in from the included sources. Examples of such data are text fragments, effect sizes, study design characteristics, year of publication, characteristics of measurement instruments, final verdicts and associated penalties in a legal system, company turnovers, sample sizes, or prevalences.

Entities to extract *

List all entities that will be extracted from each included source. Entities can be, for example, 1) variables such as values of independent and dependent variables, and potential moderators (e.g., means, standard deviations); 2) estimations of associations between variables or effect sizes (e.g., Pearson's r or Cohen's d); 3) qualitative data fragments (e.g., interview material or synthesized themes); 4) descriptions of the used methods such as the included studies' designs, sample sizes, sample characteristics, time between data collection sessions, and blinding procedures; 5) metadata such as authors, institutions, and year of publication; 6) and (other) risk of bias indicators.

1. General study information

- Author(s)
- Year of publication
- Title of study
- Journal/source
- Country of origin
- Funding source
- Conflicts of interest

2. Study characteristics

- Study design (e.g., qualitative, mixed-method, case study, pilot study, RCT)
- Study objective(s)
- Theoretical or conceptual framework (if reported)

3. Population characteristics

- Sample description
 - age range, mean age, sex distribution, health status (comorbidities), physical functioning status (no/mild/severe mobility impairments incl. indicators), cognitive functioning status (no/mild/severe mobility impairments incl. indicators)
- Inclusion/exclusion criteria for participants
- Sample size
- Other stakeholders involved (e.g., designers, clinicians, caregivers, policymakers)

4. Participatory approach characteristics

- Type of participatory approach (e.g., co-design, co-creation, participatory action research, user-centered design, living lab)
- Phase(s) of participation (e.g., needs assessment, design, development, evaluation)
- Methods and tools used for participation (e.g., workshops, interviews, focus groups, iterative testing, online feedback)
- Level of involvement of older adults (e.g., consultation, collaboration, co-decision-making)
- Duration and frequency of participation
- Reported adherence to participatory design principles or frameworks

5. Technology characteristics

- Type of technology developed or implemented (e.g., wearable device, mobile app, exergame, telehealth system)
- Target behavior or function (e.g., physical activity promotion, mobility, balance, motivation)
- Technology readiness level (prototype vs. implemented intervention)
- Setting of use (community, clinical, rehabilitation, home)

6. Reported outcomes and evaluation

- Measures of success or efficacy of the participatory approach (e.g., user satisfaction, usability, engagement, feasibility)
- Physical activity or behavioral outcomes (if applicable)
- Methods used to assess impact (e.g., questionnaires, usability testing, interviews)
- Reported barriers and facilitators for participation and technology development
- Effects of participatory approaches on intervention design, adoption, or sustainability

7. Contextual and methodological notes

- Geographical, cultural, and socioeconomic context

- Institutional or funding setting (e.g., academic–industry collaboration)
- Ethical considerations and reporting of participant consent
- Main limitations noted by the authors
- Authors’ recommendations for future research or practice

Extraction stages *

Describe the stages you will use for extraction. Examples of stages are: a training stage, a reliability verification stage, and a final extraction stage; or first extracting primary data and in a second stage risk of bias information; or two extractors working sequentially or in parallel. Also indicate for each stage whether the extraction is done by a computer (e.g., AI), a human, or a computer supervised by a human.

Data extraction will be conducted in two stages by human reviewers.

In the first stage, one reviewer will perform data extraction using a standardized data charting form developed for this review. The form will be piloted on a small sample of studies (e.g., 3–5) to ensure clarity and consistency in the extracted items.

In the second stage, a second reviewer will independently verify the extracted data for accuracy and completeness. Any discrepancies will be discussed and resolved by consensus, or, if necessary, with input from a third reviewer.

Extraction will be performed manually (no AI-assisted extraction tools will be used).

Extractor instructions *

List the instructions provided to the extractors (i.e., those performing the data extraction). You can also specify which file in the associated OSF project contains these instructions.

You may attach up to 5 file(s) to this question. Files cannot total over 5GB in size.

Extractor masking *

If masking is used, describe the procedure used to blind extractors from the research questions, hypotheses, and/or specific roles of each entity to extract in this review. For example, extractors can be research assistants who are not informed of the study’s background or research questions, but who are trained to extract entities using the coding instructions you developed for each entity; or entity extraction can be crowdsourced to citizen scientists.

Extractors will not be blinded.

Extraction reliability *

For each extraction round, list the number of extractors and the procedure used to ensure independent extraction (this can also mean that you declare that you use one extractor, or will not implement procedures to ensure that the extractions are conducted independently). Also explain the test you will use, if any, to assess extractor agreement.

Data extraction will be conducted by one reviewer. No formal test of inter-extractor agreement will be performed. To ensure data accuracy, 10% of the studies will be checked by a second reviewer. Any discrepancies identified will be discussed and corrected.

Extraction reconciliation procedure *

For each extraction round, describe the procedure to deal with divergent extraction decisions (if applicable, i.e., if you use more than one extractor).

Discrepancies identified during the 10% double-check will be discussed between the two reviewers and resolved by consensus. If a substantial number of inconsistencies are detected, the proportion of studies verified by the second reviewer will be increased until extraction consistency is ensured.

Extraction procedure justification *

Extraction procedures are often compromises, balancing pragmatic considerations with scientific rigour. Here, describe the justifications for your decisions about the justification of each entity that will be extracted, the extraction rounds, reliability assurance, and reconciliation procedures.

n.a

Data management and sharing *

Describe whether and how you will share the files with the extracted entities (as specified in the corresponding field above; i.e., everything extracted from every source, including metadata, method characteristics, variables, associations, etc). List both the file format (e.g., CSV, XLSX, RData), the repository, and any potential embargos or conditions for access. Describe efforts made to share FAIR, 5-star open data, if any such efforts will be made.

All extracted data will be submitted as supplementary material in the version of the manuscript submitted for peer-review.

Miscellaneous extraction details *

Here, you can describe any details that are not captured in the other fields in this section.

Synthesis and Quality Assessment

In this section, you register the procedure for the review's synthesis: the procedure you designed to use the data that was extracted from each source to answer your research question(s). This often includes transforming the raw extracted data, verifying validity, applying predefined inference criteria, interpreting results, and presenting results. Additionally, you register procedures you designed to assess bias in individual sources and the synthesis itself.

n.a

Planned data transformations *

Describe your plans for transforming the raw extracted data. This may include converting effect sizes to other metrics (e.g., convert all metrics to Pearson correlation coefficients); recoding or (re)categorizing extracted qualitative data fragments (e.g., coding extracted music genres within an existing taxonomy); and aggregating extracted data prior to the main synthesis procedures (e.g., compute the mean of a variable over all samples in one source). Applying these transformations to the raw extracted entities from the Extraction section should yield data that corresponds to the variables of interest listed in the Review Methods section.

n.a

Missing data *

Describe how you will deal with missing data (i.e., cases where it is not possible to extract one or more entities from the source material, and your efforts to obtain the missing information, for example by contacting the authors, are not fruitful).

n.a

Data validation *

Describe your process of ensuring that the data are correct and useful (e.g., identifying outliers, identifying retractions, or triangulating with other sources). Also describe your criteria for assessing data validity and how you will deal with data violating those criteria.

n.a

Quality assessment *

Describe the analyses you plan to do to assess and weigh the quality of the included sources with respect to your research question(s). Examples of tools to use for quality evaluation are Cochrane's Risk of Bias tool, GRADE, and GRADE-CERQual.

n.a

Synthesis plan *

Describe the specific procedure you will apply to arrive at an answer to the research question(s). For example, in meta-analyses this is the full analysis plan, including any planned subgroup analyses and moderator analyses, the (multilevel) model specification, and preferably the analysis code. For a qualitative review, it is the procedure you plan to use to collate your results into a coherent picture. If you distinguish synthesis tiers (e.g., primary and secondary analysis, or confirmatory and exploratory analyses), list them and indicate which procedures you plan to use for each. Also specify what you will do if parts of the plan can't be properly executed.

The synthesis will follow a narrative and descriptive approach consistent with JBI and PRISMA-ScR guidance. Extracted data will first be organized in tabular form to provide an overview of study characteristics (e.g., study design, population, participatory approach, type of technology, and reported outcomes).

In the next stage, findings will be synthesized narratively to identify patterns, similarities, and differences across studies. A thematic grouping will be applied to address the primary and secondary research questions, focusing on:

- (1) the types of participatory approaches used,
- (2) the technologies developed through these approaches,
- (3) the level of involvement of older adults,
- (4) measures of success or efficacy, and
- (5) barriers and facilitators of implementation.

Where possible, data will be summarized using frequency counts (e.g., number of studies per participatory approach or technology type) to complement the qualitative synthesis.

If data are too heterogeneous or insufficient to categorize meaningfully, the synthesis will rely on descriptive summaries only. No quantitative or meta-analytic methods will be applied.

Criteria for conclusions / inference criteria *

If you plan to draw your conclusions based on pre-specified criteria (e.g., a minimal effect size of interest, a significance level, or a saturation point), list these here.

n.a

Synthesist blinding *

Describe the procedure, if any, used to blind synthesists (i.e., the persons synthesizing the extracted data to arrive at answers to your research question(s)) from the research questions, hypotheses, and/or specific roles of each extracted entity/variable in this review. For example, for meta-analyses, an analyst external to the main research team can be engaged to perform the analyses without knowing the study's hypotheses. For qualitative reviews, for the synthesis, other researchers can be involved who are unaware of and are not informed about the research process and expectations.

n.a

Synthesis reliability *

List the number of synthesists and the procedure used to ensure independent synthesis (this can also mean that you declare that you use one synthesist, or will not implement procedures to ensure that the syntheses are conducted independently).

n.a

Synthesis reconciliation procedure *

Describe the procedure to deal with divergent synthesis decisions (if applicable).

n.a

Publication bias analyses *

Describe the analyses you plan to do to assess publication bias (if any). For an overview of commonly used publication bias correction methods, see Table 1 in <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0215052>

n.a

Sensitivity analyses / robustness checks *

Describe the sensitivity analyses or robustness checks you plan to conduct (if any).

n.a

Synthesis procedure justification *

Extraction procedures are sometimes compromises, balancing pragmatic considerations with scientific rigour. Here, describe the justifications for your decisions about your planned transformations (e.g., if based on assumptions, how do you know those are feasible), your data integrity and missing data checks and corrections, your synthesis plan, the criteria you chose to drive your conclusions/inferences (if any), and your procedures for blinding, and reliability assurance/reconciliation if you use multiple synthesists.

n.a

Synthesis data management and sharing *

Describe whether and how you will share the files with the analysis scripts, notes, and outputs. List both the file format (e.g., R scripts, RMarkdown files, plain text files, Open Document files), the repository, and any potential embargos or conditions for access. See <https://osf.io/5nk92> for a generic example of an analysis script.

n.a

Miscellaneous synthesis details *

Here, you can describe any details that are not captured in the other fields in this section.

n.a